

Necessary and Sufficient Conditions for Primality in Integer Sequences

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Abstract:

This note presents necessary and sufficient conditions under which certain numerical sequences produce prime numbers. The proofs of the theorems are obtained rigorously using special fractions of the type “Rio” introduced by the author. Such direct conditions for primality have not been previously established in the literature.

Keywords: Arithmetic progressions; primality criteria; Linear sequences; Necessary and sufficient conditions; Number theory; Prime numbers; Rio-type fractions

Theorem 1 For the sequence $x_a = 4a+1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq k^2 + k - n^2 \quad k \geq 1 \quad n \in [0, k-1]$$

Theorem 1.1 For the sequence $x_a = 4a+1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq (2n+1)k - n^2 \quad k \geq 1 \quad n \in [1, k]$$

Theorem 2 For the sequence $x_a = 4a-1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq k^2 + n - n^2 \quad k \geq 2 \quad n \in [1, k-1]$$

Theorem 2.1 For the sequence $x_a = 4a-1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq (2n+1)k - (n^2+n) \quad k \geq 2 \quad n \in [1, k-1]$$

Theorem 3 For the sequence $x_a = 6a+1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq 6n(k-n) + k$$

$$a \neq 6n(k-n) - k \quad \text{where } n < k \quad k \geq 2, \quad n \in [1, k-1]$$

Theorem 4 For the sequence $x_a = 6a+1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq (6k-1)n - k$$

$$a \neq (6k+1)n + k$$

Theorem 5 For the sequence $x_a = 6a-1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq 6k(k-n) + n$$

$$a \neq 6k(k-n) - n \quad k \geq 1, \quad n \in [0, k-1]$$

Theorem 6 For the sequence $x_a = 6a-1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq (6k-1)n + k$$

$$a \neq (6k+1)n - k$$

Theorem 7 For the sequence $x_a = 8a+1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq 2k^2 + k - 2n^2$$

$$a \neq 2k^2 - k - 2n^2 \quad k \geq 1, \quad n \in [0, k-1]$$

Theorem 8 For the sequence $x_a = 16a+1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq 4k^2 + k - n^2 \quad n < 2k \quad k \geq 1 \quad n \in [0, 2k)$$

$$a \neq 4k^2 - k - n^2$$

Theorem 9 For the sequence $x_a = 12a+1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq 3k^2 + k - 3n^2 \quad n < k \quad k \geq 1 \quad n \in [0, k-1]$$

$$a \neq 3k^2 - k - 3n^2$$

Theorem 10 For the sequence $x_a = 36a+1$,

a necessary and sufficient condition for x_a to be prime is:

$$a \neq 9k^2 + k - n^2 \quad n < 3k \quad k \geq 1 \quad n \in [0, 3k)$$

$$a \neq 9k^2 - k - n^2$$

Final Remark

Theorems 1 and 2 provide a constructive criterion for the primality of the key classes of numbers of the form

$4a \pm 1$, which include all prime numbers greater than 2.

Corollary 1. The primality of the sequence $2^n + 1$ follows from the primality of numbers of the form $4a+1$.

Corollary 2. The primality of the number p^2+1 for $p>1$ (where p is a natural number) is reduced to the problem of determining the primality of numbers of the form $4n^2+1$, which is a special case of the problem of determining the primality of numbers of the form $4a+1$